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Opportunities for Digital Agricultural Education in National Education Policy-2020

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During COVID-19 pandemic most Indian states have transferred their classrooms to the cloud, frequently cooperating with others, and classrooms resemble the screen of a desktop or laptop computer. Zoom, Google Meet, YouTube, Skype, and WebEx are a few examples. Become the new face of teaching classrooms in which teachers interact with their learners online and educate virtually. In one sense, this shifting paradigm of teaching opens new horizons for learning; nevertheless, it also causes a problem in another sense, where agricultural education, which is mostly centred on practical and field-based instruction, suffers a lot. Some initiatives of government of India for agricultural digital education are DIKSHA, SWAYAM online courses, UG/PG MOOCs, e-PG Pathashala, e-Content courseware in UG subjects, SWAYAMPRAKASHA, CEC-UGC YouTube channel, National Digital Library, Shodhganga, e-Shodh Sindhu and Vidwan, etc. For school students as well as UG and PG level education, it is extremely difficult to bring all learners under the same platform in equal manner where several challenges of basic infrastructure development is in its midstream and technology reach is awaited. The study conducted in UAS, Dharwad regarding utilization of ICT tools by faculty and students in agricultural education. Study revealed that (38%) faculty were using ICT tools at low extent followed by (32%) and (30%) medium extent and high extent respectively. In case of students, medium level utilization of ICT tools was more (42.67%) followed by low (29.33%) and high level (28%) respectively. There is ample scope for adopting ICT in teaching and learning on farm Universities under NEP-2020.